

Behaviour of Vanadyl Porphyrin Complexes on TLC

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The behaviour of a vanadium porphyrin complexes concentrate obtained from Darius crude oil has been studied on tlc using a variety of solvent combinations and silica gel as the adsorbent. Reasonably good separation has been achieved with three solvent combinations in one dimensional run. Acetonitrile and acetonitrile, benzene, cyclohexane (3 : 5 : 11.3) afforded the best results in a double run.

EXTENSIVE work has been done on the behaviour of porphyrins from biological sources on paper and thin layer chromatography. Various solvent systems have been recommended for the separation of porphyrin dicarboxylic acids and methyl esters of porphyrins, chlorins and related compounds on tlc¹⁻⁷. Two dimensional chromatography was successfully carried out by Elder on porphyrin methyl esters which were poorly differentiated in one dimensional systems⁸. Besides silica gel, other adsorbents tried were talc⁹⁻¹⁰ and cellulose¹¹. Application of paper and thin layer chromatography in the study of porphyrins has been reviewed by Falk¹² and Doss¹³, respectively. Work on the tlc behaviour of metal porphyrin complexes, on the other hand, has been limited to the study of chlorophylls, Cu and Zn complexes of certain porphyrins⁴ and synthetic samples of V, Ni and Cu-complexes of tetraphenyl porphins¹⁴.

As regards petroporphyrins, paper chromatography has been frequently employed for understanding the composition of porphyrin aggregates (demetallated porphyrins)^{15, 16}. Little information, however, is available about the behaviour of these porphyrins on tlc. Only recently Didyk *et al*¹⁷ have reported the isolation of five porphyrins from La Paz, a cretaceous crude oil, using this technique. To the best of the present authors' knowledge there is no report on the behaviour of petroporphyrins (metal porphyrin complexes from petroleum) on tlc. In course of our work on the isolation of metal porphyrin complexes from Darius crude, a crude from off-shore field in Iran, a study of the behaviour of petroporphyrins concentrate on tlc was necessary for understanding its composition.

Experimental

Material: The vanadium complex concentrates were prepared from Darius crude (Table 1). This crude is from off-shore field in Iran and has the highest metal content [vanadium : 25 and nickel : 10 ppm (Table 2)] among all the crude oils presently

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF DARIUS CRUDE

Density, d_4^{15}	0.852
API gravity	94.49
RVP at 37.8°, Kg/cm ²	0.94
Kinematic viscosity, cS at 37.8°	5.06
50°	9.98
Pour point, °C	- 90
Carbon residue Conradson, %wt	3.8
Sulphur, total, %wt	2.4
Characterisation factor	11.9
Water content, %v	Trace
Sediment, %wt	0.0007
Salt content, %wt	0.0008
lbs/1000 bbl	1.0
Ash, %wt	0.006
Calorific value, cal/g	10,300

TABLE 2—METAL CONTENT OF THE CRUDE (ppm)

Vanadium	25.0
Nickel	10.0
Iron	2.0
Copper	0.5
Magnesium	Not detected

being processed in India. The crude, topped upto 140°, was deasphalted using propane. The asphalt, thus obtained, was adsorbed on kieselguhr and preferentially extracted with acetonitrile containing small amounts of benzene affording the initial metal porphyrin complexes concentrate. The vanadium porphyrin complex concentrate (Conc. D₁; Fig. 1) was prepared by elution chromatography using silica gel. Vanadium porphyrin complexes have characteristic visible spectra^{18, 19}. This property has been used to determine the presence of these complexes in various fractions. Similar techniques for isolation and characterisation have been used by earlier workers as well^{20, 21}. Fig. 2 illustrates the visible spectrum of the concentrate prepared.

All the solvents used were of L. R. quality. TLC plates (5 × 20 cm; thickness 0.3 mm) were prepared by using a slurry of silica gel G (E. Merck) in water and later activated at 110-20° for 1 hr. The oxalic acid coated plates were prepared by

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* VPC VANADIUM PORPHYRIN COMPLEXES, NiPC NICKEL PORPHYRIN COMPLEXES, NON MPC NON METAL PORPHYRIN COMPLEXES
 * ADSORBENT FOR CHROMATOG SILICA GEL, A/S IN BRACKET M MAJOR, S SMALL, T TRACES

Fig. 1. Preparation of VPO concentrate from asphalt.

Fig. 2. V-Prophyrin complexes concentration in benzene. conc. 0.63% (w/v) conc. 0.63% (w/v)

making the slurry in 0.5 N oxalic acid solution and for buffered plates in acetic acid (0.2 M; 48 ml) and sodium acetate (0.2 M; 12 ml) [pH 4.05]. The sample was applied in acetone or benzene solution. The time for saturation of the chamber and development of the plate was 30 and 10 min, respectively. The temperature varied from 25 to 30°. The solvent was allowed to run only 8 cm from the base. The air dried developed plates were sprayed with cyclohexane and viewed under uv light (350 nm). Esterification of the sample (in methanol) was carried out using ethereal solution of diazomethane.

Tables 3 and 4 list the various solvent systems tried, the resolution obtained and the colour and R_f values of the spots. Fig. 3 shows how the spots appeared on the chromatograms.

Results and Discussion

Use of solvent combinations already reported in the literature as developing solvents for porphyrins did not yield encouraging results. It was soon

B—Blue P—Pink V—Violet Br—Brown R—Red Y—Yellow

Fig. 8.

TABLE 3—TLC of VOPO CONC.

Solvent system	Composition	TLC Pattern	R _f	Appearance under uv light
A	Acetone (1)- <i>n</i> -Heptane (1)	4 spots and residue	0.53	Yellow
			0.67	Red
			0.83	Violet
			0.91	Blue
B	Acetonitrile (3)- Benzene (5)- Cyclohexane (11.3) in NH ₃ -atmosphere	4 spots, 1 tail and residue	0.55	Yellow
			0.68	Pink
			0.80	Brown
			0.92	Blue
			0.97	Blue
C	Acetonitrile	5 spots, 2 tails and a residue (on oxalic acid coated plate)	0.27	Blue
			0.48	Blue
			0.62	Violet
			0.72	Yellow
			0.88	Yellow

TABLE 4—TLC OF ESTERIFIED VOPO CONC.

Solvent system	Composition	TLC pattern	R _f	Appearance under uv light
D	Acetone (1)- <i>n</i> -Heptane (1)	4 spots, 1 tail and residue	0.46	Yellow
			0.66	Red
			0.80	Violet
			0.91	Blue
E	Acetonitrile (3)- Benzene (9)- Cyclohexane (7.2)	4 spots, 2 tails and residue	0.09	Yellow
			0.36	Yellow
			0.45	Pink
			0.87	Blue
			0.21	Blue
F	Acetonitrile	6 spots, 2 tails and residue	0.37	Yellow
			0.67	Blue
			0.75	Violet
			0.84	Blue
			0.96	Pink
			0.24	Blue
			0.54	Violet
G	Cyclohexane (2)- Ethanol (1)	6 spots, 2 tails and residue	0.62	Yellow
			0.74	Violet
			0.87	Yellow
			0.96	Blue
			0.34	Yellow
			0.43	Violet
			0.58	Blue
			0.60	Violet
H	Cyclohexane (2)- Benzene (1)- Ethanol (1)	7 spots, 1 tail and residue	0.68	Blue
			0.75	Pink
			0.91	Blue
			0.26	Yellow
			0.51	Violet
			0.70	Blue
I	(C) Acetonitrile (B) Acetonitrile (3)- Benzene (5)- Cyclohexane(11.3)	7 spots, 3-tails and residue	0.78	Violet
			0.85	Blue
			0.90	Pink
			0.96	Blue
			0.96	Blue

realized that solvent combinations, degree of saturation of the chamber, amount of the sample spotted and the distance moved by it were the various factors affecting the separation. Moreover, the metal porphyrin complexes lacked the sensitive fluorescence of the uncomplexed pigments and their characteristic colour could be detected at relatively high levels of concentration where the danger of tailing exists. Use was, therefore, made of an indirect method of spraying the air dried developed plates with cyclohexane before viewing them under uv light. *Iso*-octane or a dilute solution

of fluoranthene in cyclohexane¹² was found to be equally effective amongst the various solvent combinations attempted for studying the behaviour of the petroporphyrins concentrate on tic. The best resolution, however, was obtained with acetone-*n*-heptane (1 : 1), affording four spots and a residue. The solvent was allowed to move a distance of only 8 cm as beyond this distance the spots had a tendency to diffuse. The spots were blue, brown, pink and yellow in colour with R_f values of 0.91, 0.83, 0.67 and 0.53, respectively. The major problem in the chromatography of the metal porphyrin complexes was their tendency to tail. To overcome this difficulty ammonia atmosphere¹³ and oxalic acid coated plates¹⁴ were tried. Acetonitrile-benzene-cyclohexane (3 : 5 : 11.3) and the latter systems, respectively but were in no way superior to acetone-*n*-heptane (1 : 1) (cf. Table 3). Sodium acetate buffered plates¹⁵ did not bring results.

As petroporphyrins are known to occur sometime as carboxylic acids¹⁶, the esterified sample (diazomethane) was subjected to extensive thin layer chromatography using a number of solvent combinations. Table 2 lists the various solvent systems affording a reasonably good resolution of the esterified petroporphyrin concentrate. Resolution was greatly improved by the use of solvents systems like acetonitrile; cyclohexane-ethanol (2 : 1) and cyclohexane-benzene-ethanol (2 : 1 : 1) resolving the starting material into seven spots, two tails and a residue. The spots were of different colours and nicely distinguishable from one another. The last two solvent combinations probably gave the best resolution but suffered from homogeneity problem at lower temperature.

Another attempt to further improve the resolution, if possible, was made by running the tic plates in two solvent systems. The sample was run in the first solvent system (8 cm with respect to the solvent), the plate air dried and rerun the same distance in the second solvent in the same direction. Acetonitrile (in the first run) and acetonitrile-benzene-cyclohexane (3 : 5 : 11.3) in the second run resolved the esterified concentrate into seven spots, three tails and a residue. This combination was found to be the best among all the solvent systems tried.

Conclusion : The petroporphyrins concentrate prepared from Darius crude could be resolved satisfactorily on silica gel plates using acetone-*n*-heptane (1 : 1) as the developing solvent. Degree of saturation of the chamber, amount of the sample spotted and the distance moved by it were the various factors affecting the separation. The resolution could be improved considerably by running the esterified sample in acetonitrile; cyclohexane-ethanol (2 : 1) and cyclohexane-benzene-ethanol (2 : 1 : 1) in one dimension. Best results were, however, obtained with acetonitrile and acetonitrile-benzene-cyclohexane (3 : 5 : 11.3) in a double run.

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